

UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM

THE RIGHT TO HEALTH VERSUS THE RIGHT TO WEALTH

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**Implications of Tobacco
Plain Packaging Regulations
on International Trade and
Investment Law**

'...if you smoke, a cigarette pack is one of the few things you use regularly that makes a statement about you. A cigarette pack is the only thing you take out of your pocket 20 times a day and lay out for everyone to see. That's a lot different than buying your soap powder in generic packaging...'

Brown and Williamson (American Tobacco Company) employee stated on packages promotional potential

ABSTRACT

Tobacco companies have expressed concerns that the latest development in Australia and Uruguay's plain cigarette packaging initiative breaches international obligations under trade and investment agreements. This article begins by taking a look into the background of cigarette packaging. It then goes on to examine latest developments in the field of tobacco plain packaging on the world stage, and lastly provides an analysis on the claim posed by the cigarette companies that this trend is incompatible with the international legislation. It concludes that the general move towards plain packaging undertaken by Australia, Uruguay and many other countries is consistent with the international obligations undertaken by countries and that concerns about plain packaging violating international trade and investment law should not stop countries from implementing plain packaging in their health agenda. Lastly, this thesis provides several possible methods for reconciliation of the rights of states and the rights of investors.

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INTRODUCTION

International investment agreements are created and signed by countries with the purpose of creating, liberalising and protecting investments and promoting economic development. International investment agreements (IIAs) promote all types of investments, including some investments that spark debates- such as tobacco products.¹

Tobacco products have been proven to have serious consequences for public health and tobacco consumption has been a concern of the international community for a long time.² Despite the public opposition, it is undoubted that the tobacco industry worldwide is a very powerful force. So powerful that it has the influence to push governments to change their policies. One of the tobacco industry's most commonly used tactics to undermine different countries' power to accept and implement laws that harm the power of tobacco companies is the threat of litigation.³

Lawsuits or just the threat of lawsuits can have a chilling effect on a government that wants to implement a tobacco control regulation. And tobacco companies have increasingly used different international investment agreements to target countries that adopt stringent tobacco rules. These actions have the purpose of trying to make countries that already have legislation put in place change their regulations and intimidate other countries that have not implemented that type of regulations yet.⁴

In 2011, the Philip Morris International started a case against Uruguay⁵, challenging Uruguay's two public health measures whose aim was to restrict tobacco products from having different packages and variants, but instead have only one, plain package; and increase the health warning on cigarette packages from fifty percent to eighty percent of the surface of the

¹ UNITED NATIONS CONFERENCE ON TRADE AND DEVELOPMENT (ed), 'Development implications of international investment agreements: IIA MONITOR No. 2 (2007) International investment agreements' (2007) <https://unctad.org/en/Docs/webiteiia20072_en.pdf>.

² WTO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control 2003 (World Health Organisation).

³ Jane Kelsey, 'Regulatory Chill: Learnings from New Zealand's Plain Packaging Tobacco Law' (2017) 17(2) 21 <<https://lr.law.qut.edu.au/article/view/701>>, accessed on 22 March 2019.

⁴ Eric Crosbie and George Thomson, 'Regulatory chills: tobacco industry legal threats and the politics of tobacco standardised packaging in New Zealand' (2018) 131(1473) The New Zealand medical journal 25, accessed on 22 March 2019.

⁵ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* Case No. ARB/10/7 (ICSID).

package- leaving only twenty percent of the surface for trademarks and logos of the brand.⁶ Philip Morris claimed that this regulation constituted expropriation of the company's intellectual property rights⁷ and that it also violated the international investment agreement under which the investment was created.⁸

Philip Morris Asia followed this example and several months later initiated a case against Australia on national level- challenging its regulation prohibiting any use of trademark on its packaging- on the same basis- expropriation of intellectual property.⁹ They also initiated investment treaty claim¹⁰ under the BIT signed between Australia and Hong Kong¹¹ followed by a case in the World Trade Organisation (WTO).¹²

These lawsuits cost millions of dollars and are very lengthy- which has scared off some countries that intended to create plain packaging legislation. But others have continued with their intentions of implementing plain packaging regulations. United Kingdom has implemented the Standardised Packaging of Tobacco Products 2015¹³ which unsurprisingly led to a challenge to the validity of the regulation in the UK High Court in 2016.¹⁴ A Decree by the French Parliament¹⁵ applying to cigarettes and hard- roll- tobacco came into force in

⁶ Prabhash Ranjan, 'Police Powers, Indirect Expropriation in International Investment Law, and Article 31(3)(c) of the VCLT: A Critique of Philip Morris v. Uruguay' (2019) 9(1) Asian Journal of International Law 98 <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/EB1C739257E355631F270A98B23F5481/S2044251318000139a.pdf/police_powers_indirect_expropriation_in_international_investment_law_and_article_313c_of_the_vclt_a_critique_of_philip_morris_v_uruguay.pdf>, accessed on 23 March 2019.

⁷ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5).

⁸ Agreement between the Swiss Confederation and the Oriental Republic of Uruguay on the Reciprocal Promotion and Protection of Investments, BIT.

⁹ *JT International SA v. Commonwealth of Australia British American Tobacco Australasia Limited v. The Commonwealth* HCA 43, [2012] (High Court of Australia).

¹⁰ *Philip Morris Asia Limited v. The Commonwealth of Australia* PCA Case No. 2012-12, [2015] (UNCITRAL).

¹¹ Agreement between the Government of Hong Kong and the Government of Australia for the Promotion and Protection of Investments 1993, BIT.

¹² *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* [2018] (World Trade Organisation Panel Body).

¹³ The Standardised Packaging of Tobacco Products Regulations 2015 2015 (The Parliament of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland).

¹⁴ *R (Philip Morris Brands Sarl & Others) v. Secretary of State for Health C-547* Case C-547/14, [2016] (Court of Justice of the European Union (Second Chamber)).

¹⁵ Decree No. 2016-1117 of 11 August 2016 on the manufacture, presentation, sale and use of tobacco products, vaping products and herbal smoking products other than tobacco 2016.

2016, being challenged that same year.¹⁶ Hungary,¹⁷ Ireland,¹⁸ Norway,¹⁹ New Zealand,²⁰ Slovenia²¹ and Romania²² have adopted laws but have not implemented them yet.

This movement poses the important question: when drafting an investment treaty where should be the balance between the powers of the State to create laws and regulate investments in its territory for the good of the people and the right of investors to secure their investment against changes of the investment environment even when this change is done in light of protection of the public and should international investment law change in the future in order to accommodate both the rights of states and the rights of investors?

In this paper, I will analyse this problem through the lenses of several legal cases on plain packaging of tobacco products.

In Chapter I, I will give an overview of the definition and purposes of plain packaging, the evidence behind the idea of plain packaging, the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control- a multilateral treaty that is in force and has been signed by more than 160 countries.²³

In Chapter II, I will focus on the existing case law; namely, the cases of Philip Morris v Australia,²⁴ the case Philip Morris initiated against Australia on domestic level,²⁵ the case Philip Morris initiated against Australia in WTO²⁶ and the case of Philip Morris V Uruguay.²⁷ I will try to conclude how and why the respective courts reached their conclusions and what do these awards mean for future cases of plain packaging measures and their implementation.

¹⁶ *Decision no. 2015-727 DC, 21 January 2016, Law for the Modernisation of Our Health system* [2016] (Constitutional Council of France).

¹⁷ Government regulation 239/2016 (16 August) on the amendment of government regulation 39/2013 (14 February) on the detailed rules of production, distribution and control of tobacco products, the combined warnings and the application of health protection fines 2016 (Hungarian Government).

¹⁸ Public Health (Standardised Packaging of tobacco) Act 2015 2015.

¹⁹ Standardized Packaging of Tobacco Products 2017 (The Parliament of Norway).

²⁰ Smoke-free Environments Regulation 2017 (Ministry of Health New Zealand).

²¹ Rules on the Plain Packaging of Tobacco Products 2020 (The Parliament of Slovenia).

²² Law on the establishment of conditions concerning the manufacture, presentation and marketing of tobacco and related products and amendments to Law No. 349/2002 on preventing the consumption of tobacco products and combating its effects 2016.

²³ Secretariat of the United Nations, 'United Nations Treaty Collection: Chapter IX Health' <<https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/MTDSG/Volume%20I/Chapter%20IX/IX-4.en.pdf>>.

²⁴ *Philip Morris Asia Limited v. The Commonwealth of Australia* (n 10).

²⁵ *JT International SA v. Commonwealth of Australia British American Tobacco Australasia Limited v. The Commonwealth* (n 9).

²⁶ *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* (n 12).

²⁷ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5).

In Chapter III, I will take a closer look at International Investment Agreements, their structure and specificity. I will comment on the meaning of investment in international investment agreements (IIAs) and try to answer the question whether intellectual property (and in that respect trade marks) fall under this category. I will cover the standards of treatment most IIAs provide to investors. Undoubtedly, the most relevant to potential claims relating to health measures is the expropriation provision. Expropriation can be related to invalidation of patents, measures to limit or completely revoke intellectual property rights of companies producing tobacco products, such as plain packaging requirement or prohibition of advertisement of cigarette and other products. The topic of indirect expropriation has been one of the most contested questions in international investment law and has created a lot of ambiguity in both states and investors. In addition to expropriation, most IIAs contain the obligation to provide investors with fair and equitable treatment (FET) and this standard is also relevant to tobacco measures.

In Chapter IV, I will focus on possible methods of reconciliation of investors' rights over their property and investment and the rights of countries to regulate and change their laws for the public good after they have signed investment agreements.

The world known cases of Philip Morris can be used as a reminder- that after all, intellectual property rights are part of IIAs and certain provisions in these IIAs can affect the host country's ability to regulate public health. However, there is a big uncertainty in this area for both investors and States- do IIAs have the potential for overlapping and inconsistent commitments on the international stage and if yes- what is more important- the right to health or the right to wealth?

Chapter I

Plain Packaging: Definition, purpose, evidence

I. WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC)

The Framework Convention on Tobacco Control²⁸ was signed in 2003 and since then 168 countries have signed it and 181 countries became party to it.²⁹ The Framework Convention contains several articles that cover plain packaging – Article 11 – Packaging and Labelling of Tobacco Products and Article 13- Tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship. Together with the guidelines to these articles, the Framework Convention have been proven by courts to be ‘evidence-based’ international instruments that can be used as a basis by countries when they create their tobacco regulations.³⁰ The FCTC and its guidelines have also been used as a reference for the reasonableness of a measure with courts even coming to the conclusion that countries do not need to conduct their own research on tobacco products and tobacco regulation but they can instead base their legislation on the scientific research and evidence provided by the FCTC.³¹

II. Definition of plain packaging

The concept of plain packaging was first introduced by the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) in 2003. An explanation of what plain packaging is is provided in paragraph 46 of the Guidelines to Article 11: ‘...measures to restrict or prohibit the use of logos, colours, brand images or promotional information on packaging other than brand names and product names displayed in a standard colour and font style.’³²

²⁸ WTO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (n 2).

²⁹ Secretariat of the United Nations (n 23).

³⁰ Check Appendix 3 for FCTC and Guidelines.

³¹ Suzanne Zhou, ‘WHO TCTC Implementation after Philip Morris v Uruguay: Five key messages from the Award’ (2016) <<https://untobaccocontrol.org/kh/legal-challenges/philip-morris-v-uruguay/?print-posts=pdf>>, accessed on 27 March 2019.

³² Guidelines for implementation of Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (Packaging and labelling of tobacco products) 2003 (World Health Organisation).

This means that on a tobacco box there should only be the name of the brand in a mandated size and health warnings, with the appearance of all brands being standardised.³³

The Guidelines to Article 11 also provide specific information on how health warnings on the tobacco pack should look like. Paragraph 12 provides that the health warnings on tobacco packaging and labelling should be 50% or more of the pack, but not less than 30% of the display areas.³⁴ Paragraph 16 of the Guidelines of Article 13 FCTC explains that ‘There should be no advertising or promotion inside or attached to the package or on individual cigarettes or other tobacco products.’³⁵

III. Purpose of plain packaging

Article 3 of the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control provides that the objective of the measures is to ‘protect the present and future generations from the devastating health, social, environmental and economic consequences of tobacco consumption’.³⁶

The purpose of plain packaging is to reduce the attractiveness of cigarettes and other tobacco products, to address the problem of some packaging design such as different colours of the packages that may suggest that some tobacco products are less harmful than others if placed in lighter packages, to eliminate tobacco packaging as a way of advertising and promoting tobacco products and to increase the effectiveness of health warnings on the pack.³⁷

IV. Evidence supporting plain packaging

When creating the plain packaging measure (and the other measures contained in the FCTC- such as measures created to reduce demand for tobacco products (Article 6- Price and Tax measures to reduce the demand for tobacco), or those aimed at regulating tobacco exposure- Article 10 FCTC or creating demand reduction measures for tobacco dependence and

³³ Check Appendix 1 and 2 for models of plain packaging boxes.

³⁴ Check Appendix 3.

³⁵ For more information, check Appendix 3 on Guidelines.

³⁶ WTO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (n 2), Article 3.

³⁷ Tobacco plain packaging: global status update 2018 (WHO, Secretariat WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control), accessed on 25 March 2019.

cessation- Article 14) countries have used empirical evidence on the harmfulness of smoking and also effects of measures intended to decrease this harmfulness.

Several studies have proven that packaging plays a big role in promoting tobacco products especially since other means of tobacco promotion such as advertisements on television are now forbidden.³⁸ Studies have shown that consumers display tobacco boxes in a social setting and use them as ‘badge products’, identifying themselves with the social image that the particular tobacco brand has.³⁹

Studies have also shown that the advertisement of tobacco products is especially harmful to young people with an estimate of 10% of student between the age of 13 to 15 smoking cigarettes worldwide.⁴⁰

Evidence has proved that health warnings on the cigarette packages, together with images of people suffering from different diseases due to tobacco consumption and the lack of branding of tobacco boxes makes consumers and non-consumers more aware of the dangers of smoking and also of the messages that the information on the boxes tries to transmit.⁴¹

Several countries have done research on the topic and the UK public health research consortium has concluded in a paper that plain packages were perceived by consumers and non-consumers as less attractive than branded packaging and that plain packs were seen as ‘containing poorer quality products.’⁴² The Irish Department of Health Review conducted a research on the topic of plain packaging and came to the conclusion that plain packaging contributes to the efficacy of health warnings on the box, reduces the appeal that cigarettes have among young people and children and reduces the false beliefs that some cigarettes are less dangerous than others based on the colour of the box.⁴³ In Australia, studies have found that after the introduction of plain

³⁸ M. Wakefield and others, ‘The cigarette pack as image: new evidence from tobacco industry documents’ (2002) 11 Suppl 1 Tobacco Control I73-80, accessed on 27 March 2019.

³⁹ Tobacco plain packaging: global status update (n 37).

⁴⁰ ‘Tobacco use among youth: a cross country comparison’ (2002) 11(3) Tobacco Control 252, accessed on 28 March 2019.

⁴¹ Mohammed Al-Hamdani, ‘The Effect of Cigarette Plain Packaging on Individuals' Health Warning Recall’ (2013) 8(3) Healthcare Policy 68, accessed on 28 March 2019.

⁴² Moodie, C. Stead, M. Bauld L. McNeill, A. Hinds, K. ‘Plain tobacco packaging: a systematic review’ (2011) <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/cms/Portals/0/PDF%20reviews%20and%20summaries/tobaccopacks_MoodiePHRC_R2_012_web.pdf?ver=2012-05-09-161542-420>, p.38-51, accessed on 28 March 2019.

⁴³ David Hammond, ‘Standardised Packaging of Tobacco Products: Evidence review, prepared on behalf of the Irish Department of Health’ (2014) <<https://health.gov.ie/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/2014-Ireland-Plain-Pack-Main-Report-Final-Report-July-26.pdf>>, accessed on 28 March 2019.

packaging, there was a decrease in positive image of cigarettes among smokers and overall reduction of the appeal of cigarette packs.⁴⁴

By creating the FCTC and implementing it in their national legislations, countries have shown their desire to oppose to tobacco companies and their attempts to pressure them in creating legislation that gives bigger rights to investors. And it has been only a matter of time for investors to initiate litigation against States and their legislation in an attempt to take back control.

⁴⁴ Victoria White, Tahlia Williams and Melanie Wakefield, 'Has the introduction of plain packaging with larger graphic health warnings changed adolescents' perceptions of cigarette packs and brands?' (2015) 24(Suppl 2) Tobacco Control ii42-ii49, accessed on 28 March 2019.

Chapter II

Case law

I. Philip Morris v Uruguay

Philip Morris v Uruguay⁴⁵ is the first case in which the matter of plain packaging was put in front of a tribunal. In 2008, Uruguay- which at the time was the Latin American country with the highest consumption of tobacco products⁴⁶- adopted the Single Presentation Requirement regulation and a presidential decree on tobacco products.⁴⁷

This caused Philip Morris Brands Sarl- a tobacco company registered in Switzerland that owns the trademarks of Marlboro, Philip Morris and L&M to initiate proceedings against Uruguay under the Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) between Uruguay and Switzerland.⁴⁸ The claim that Philip Morris had against Uruguay was that by adopting the two measures Uruguay breached its obligations under its BIT with Switzerland – by limiting the company’s ability to use its legally protected trademarks which resulted in the reduction of the market value of the company.⁴⁹

The ICSID tribunal dismissed the claims of Philip Morris and confirmed the legality of both measures with the argument that these measures had been taken with the purpose of protecting the public health. Philip Morris was ordered to pay 7 million USD to Uruguay.

The first main argument that was looked at by the tribunal was the argument put by Philip Morris that the two regulations constituted indirect expropriation of the company’s assets and trademarks.⁵⁰ Uruguay, on the other hand, argued that the measures were taken as a legitimate exercise of a country’s power to create laws for the public good and public health.⁵¹ The

⁴⁵ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5).

⁴⁶ Pei-Kan Yang, ‘The Margin of Appreciation Debate over Novel Cigarette Packaging Regulations in Philip Morris v Uruguay: A Step toward a Balanced standard of review of investment disputes’ (2018) 1(1) Brill Open Law 91 <https://brill.com/view/journals/bol/1/1/article-p91_91.xml>, accessed on 10 April 2019.

⁴⁷ Law No. 19.723 2018 (Ministry of Public Health of Uruguay).

⁴⁸ Agreement between the Swiss Confederation and the Oriental Republic of Uruguay on the Reciprocal Promotion and Protection of Investments (n 8).

⁴⁹ *Ibid.* para.274.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.* para.180.

⁵¹ *Ibid.* para.181.

Tribunal held that adoption of these laws were a valid exercise of the police powers doctrine made for the public welfare⁵² in good faith and in proportionate manner.⁵³

The second main argument put by Philip Morris was that the measures breached the fair and equitable treatment (FET) clause of the Switzerland- Uruguay BIT because they were arbitrary and did harm to the company's assets and at the same time did not further Uruguay's public health objectives in the most proportionate way.⁵⁴ To which the Court concluded that there is a margin of appreciation to the government's ability to create laws when it comes to national needs such as public health and investors should respect this margin.⁵⁵

Philip Morris also argued that the FET standard had been breached because the company had legitimate expectations that the legal environment in Uruguay would not change. The Tribunal held that legal changes could not be prevented by the FET standard as long as the State was making these changes for the public good and the changes were of 'acceptable margin'.⁵⁶ In the particular case, the Tribunal found that with the existence of the Framework Convention of Tobacco Control and emerging international concern for the harmful effects of tobacco products, stricter regulations should have been expected by Philip Morris.⁵⁷

The result of the Philip Morris v Uruguay case defending the right of the State to regulate and create laws for the public health has played a crucial role for the international investment law.⁵⁸ This case was the first one of this kind and opened the gates for several other high profile litigations that followed suit.

II. Philip Morris v Australia- BIT case

In 2011, Australia introduced the Tobacco Plain Packaging Act⁵⁹ and with it prohibited the use of trademarks, images and symbols on the tobacco packages. The law allowed only the name of the tobacco company to be displayed on the package in a standardised fashion and images of people suffering from diseases caused by tobacco use. This in practice made it very difficult

⁵² Ibid.para.287.

⁵³ Ibid.para.305.

⁵⁴ Ibid.para.310.

⁵⁵ Ibid.para.399.

⁵⁶ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5), para.423.

⁵⁷ Ibid.para.430.

⁵⁸ Ranjan (n 6)

⁵⁹ Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011.

for customers to distinguish between the different tobacco brands and took away some of the appeal of tobacco products.

Philip Morris Asia Limited- the claimant- was registered in Hong Kong and in 2011 gained ownership of the Australian subsidiary- Philip Morris Limited. As a result of the introduction of the Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011, in June 2011 Philip Morris started a case against Australia under the UNCITRAL rules claiming that this legislation, by prohibiting the use of trademarks and symbols on the tobacco packages, had restricted Philip Morris to use its trademarks. Philip Morris claimed that this restriction constituted expropriation under the Australia- Hong Kong Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT).⁶⁰ Australia denied breaching substantive obligations under the BIT and counterclaimed that Philip Morris's restructuring was launched only with the intent to benefit from the BIT.

The Philip Morris- Australia case did not reach the stage of merits. The UNCITRAL Tribunal decided that the case was inadmissible and stopped it at jurisdictional stage because it found that the initiation of the proceedings was an abuse of rights in itself. The Tribunal concluded that Philip Morris Asia Limited changed its corporate structure and acquired ownership of Philip Morris Australia with the sole purpose of initiating a case under the Australia-Hong Kong BIT. The Tribunal further explained that the Australian government has expressed its intention to create a Plain Packaging law back in 2008 and has intensively worked on its creation for several years- which was well known to the public and to Philip Morris Asia. In 2015 the UNCITRAL Tribunal concluded that Philip Morris could not have had reasonable expectation that Australia will not implement that law and on the contrary the tobacco company created, knowing that this law would be created and implemented, restructured in order to gain protection under the BIT and to materialise its claim.⁶¹

Unfortunately, since the claim did not reach the merits stage, the Tribunal did not have to decide on the problem of expropriation and fair and equitable standard raised by Philip Morris and did not have to render a verdict on the merits unlike the Tribunal in Philip Morris v Uruguay that upheld its jurisdiction and examined the merits of the case. This case started a series of legal proceedings – in international and national courts- initiated by tobacco companies against States in response to measures taken by governments with the intention to regulate packaging

⁶⁰ Agreement between the Government of Hong Kong and the Government of Australia for the Promotion and Protection of Investments (n 11).

⁶¹ Tania Voon, 'Third Strike: The WTO Panel Reports Upholding Australia's Tobacco Plain Packaging Scheme: Pre-edited draft forthcoming in (2019)' [2018] Journal of World Investment and Trade 1 <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3275074>, accessed on 10 April 2019.

and was an indication that tobacco companies will not back off easily even against rich countries such as Australia.

III. Philip Morris v Australia- High Court

On 28th of February 2012, just 8 months after Philip Morris had initiated its case against Australia under UNCITRAL rules, four major tobacco producers- British American Tobacco (BAT), Imperial Tobacco, Japan Tobacco and Philip Morris- challenged the Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011, in the High Court of Australia.⁶² The companies argued that the High Court of Australia was the forum in which proceedings should be initiated since the High Court had jurisdiction ‘on matters arising under the Constitution, or involving its interpretation’. The tobacco companies’ claims were based on the argument that the Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011 (TPPA) has breached their trademarks and constrained their enjoyment of intellectual property. Philip Morris and others opened their claim under section 51 (xxxix) of the Constitution of Australia which provides that the Parliament of Australia has the power to make laws for peace and order but when making these laws Parliament should do so on just terms when it comes to the acquisition of property from any state or person. They argued that intellectual property rights were property for the purposes of Article 51 (xxxix) and by restricting the use of trademarks and symbols on tobacco packages, Australia had acquired property from them and this acquisition was not made on just terms as requested by Article 51 (xxxix). Philip Morris and others argued that since legislation that violates Article 51 (xxxix) is invalid, the TPPA should be invalidated and plain packaging requirements should be abolished.⁶³

The Australian High Court upheld the TPPA and concluded that despite the fact that intellectual rights can be perceived as property, the TPPA’s implementation did not amount to acquisition of property. Justice Hayne concluded that ‘there can be no acquisition of property without the Commonwealth or another acquiring an interest in property, however slight or insubstantial it may be’.⁶⁴ Justice Gummow concluded that ‘there was sufficient impairment, at least of the

⁶² *JT International SA v. Commonwealth of Australia British American Tobacco Australasia Limited v. The Commonwealth* (n 9).

⁶³ Daniel Fletcher (ed), *Case Note: JT International SA v Commonwealth: Tobacco Plain Packaging* (35, Sydney Law Review 2013), accessed on 11 April 2019.

⁶⁴ *JT International SA v. Commonwealth of Australia British American Tobacco Australasia Limited v. The Commonwealth*, para. 169.

statutory intellectual property of the plaintiffs, to amount to taking, but there was no acquisition of any property'.⁶⁵

Although there was not a judgement on the merits of plain packaging as a policy, its legality or the evidence supporting it, nor there was a balance between the rights of tobacco companies and the interests of public health, there were several very important messages that the High Court passed throughout its reasoning.⁶⁶

The Court concluded that trademarks are rights of negative character- they can be used to exclude others from enjoyment of the intellectual property, and not give the owner of the intellectual property positive rights to enjoy his property in any scenario. The Court also concluded that the tobacco companies have lost commercial value due to their inability to promote and advertise their products in a free manner, but it also concluded that commercial value is not under Constitutional protection.⁶⁷ Justice Hayne and Bell also clarified that the TPPA is not substantially different from other regulations that require health warnings and hence, should not be treated in a different manner.⁶⁸ Justice Crennan further explained that the TPPA Scheme allows companies to continue to use brand names on tobacco packages, although in a regulated and standardised style, which does not fully deprive companies of enjoyment of their intellectual property and consumer base.⁶⁹ The biggest affirmation of TPPA came from Justice French, who observed that intellectual property rights cannot exist in a vacuum but are related to other areas of law and 'are created by statute in order to serve public purposes'.⁷⁰ He added that the TPPA 'reflects a serious judgement that the public benefit to be derived from the regulatory scheme outweigh those public benefits derived from intellectual property rights'.⁷¹

⁶⁵ Ibid. para. 101.

⁶⁶ Jonathan Liberman, 'Plainly Constitutional: The Upholding of Plain Packaging by the High Court of Australia' (2013) 39(2 and 3) American Journal of Law and Medicine 361 <http://www.mccabecentre.org/downloads/liberman_plainly_constitutional_final.pdf>, accessed on 12 April 2019.

⁶⁷ JT International SA v. Commonwealth of Australia British American Tobacco Australia Limited v The Commonwealth HCA 43, (2012) (High Court of Australia), para. 365.

⁶⁸ Ibid. para. 181.

⁶⁹ Ibid. para. 290.

⁷⁰ Ibid. para. 35.

⁷¹ Ibid. para. 43.

IV. Philip Morris v Australia – WTO case

Just two weeks after Philip Morris started the proceedings in the High Court of Australia, Ukraine challenged the TPPA in WTO.⁷² Ukraine's interest in the dispute were not based on tobacco trade between the two countries but on political pressure imposed by Philip Morris's subsidiary in Ukraine.

Ukraine claimed that the TPPA breaches Article III: 4 of the GATT 1994⁷³- national treatment on internal taxation and regulation- by providing better treatment to Australian tobacco companies than to foreign companies incorporated in Australia under BITs. Ukraine also claimed that TPPA breaches Articles 2.1 and 2.2 of TBT Agreement⁷⁴ by creating technical regulations that accord treatment less favourable to products imported to Australia than products of national origin. Ukraine also claimed that TPPA is inconsistent with Australia's international obligations under the TRIPS Agreement⁷⁵ and more precisely Article 1, 2, 3, 15, 16, 20 and 27.

On June 28, 2018, the WTO panel published its decision on the Ukrainian claims.⁷⁶ The Panel found in favour of Australia on all claims, which was the third big plain packaging win for Australia. The Panel concluded that plain packaging plays an important role in public health protection and the consequences of not achieving plain packaging's objective would be 'exceptionally grave'.⁷⁷

On the challenge of trade restrictiveness, the Panel found that TPPA was not more-trade restrictive than necessary under Article 2.1 and 2.2 of TBT because the aim of the Regulation-protecting public health- was a legitimate one, there was no alternative that would be less trade-restrictive and would provide equivalent level of public health protection.⁷⁸ The Panel also concluded that plain packaging in its core is trade-restrictive because by reducing the overall

⁷² AUSTRALIA – CERTAIN MEASURES CONCERNING TRADEMARKS AND OTHER PLAIN PACKAGING REQUIREMENTS APPLICABLE TO TOBACCO PRODUCTS AND PACKAGING 15 March 2012 (Request for consultation by Ukraine, World Trade Organisation).

⁷³ GATT 1994: General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (World Trade Organisation).

⁷⁴ Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade 1994 (World Trade Organisation).

⁷⁵ Agreement on Trade-related aspects of intellectual property rights 1995 (World Trade Organisation).

⁷⁶ AUSTRALIA – CERTAIN MEASURES CONCERNING TRADEMARKS, GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS AND OTHER PLAIN PACKAGING REQUIREMENTS APPLICABLE TO TOBACCO PRODUCTS AND PACKAGING [2018] (World Trade Organisation Panel Body), para. 7.248-7.251.

⁷⁷ Ibid. para. 7.2592, para.7.1310.

⁷⁸ Ibid. para. 7.1324-7.1731.

consumption of tobacco products it reduces the import of tobacco products in a country but this should be weighed against the overall contribution of plain packaging to public health.⁷⁹

On the claim of intellectual property rights, the Panel concluded that although plain packaging is an encumbrance to intellectual property rights, it is not unjustifiable under Article 20 because there is an important social interest that is protected by it,⁸⁰ making tobacco packages standardised is important for achieving protection of public health⁸¹ and overall plain packaging provides sufficient support for the restrictions TPPA imposes.⁸²

The WTO panel's decision, together with the decision in the High Court of Australia and the UNCITRAL award, show clearly that the direction in which international law is moving is contrary to tobacco industry's arguments that plain packaging breaches international and national legislation. Which can encourage more countries to move on with their plain packaging measures.⁸³

V. Other illustrative cases

In 2015, the UK implemented the Standardised Packaging of Tobacco Products Regulations which lead to a challenge by British American Tobacco. In 2016, the Court of Appeal of England and Wales concluded that plain packaging is consistent with the legislative powers of the UK Parliament⁸⁴ and upheld the High Court's decision⁸⁵ that plain packaging does not violate the right to property, there is no positive right to use a trademark and the measure is proportional to the objective it seeks to achieve.

In 2016, France also implemented plain packaging legislation.⁸⁶ This provoked series of challenges to the measure.⁸⁷ The French State Council rejected these challenges and concluded

⁷⁹ Ibid. para.7.1208, para. 7. 1310.

⁸⁰ Ibid. para.7.2592.

⁸¹ Ibid. Para.7.2593.

⁸² Ibid. para.7.2604.

⁸³ McCabe Centre for Law and Cancer, 'An initial overview of the WTO panel decision in Australia- Plain Packaging' (2018) <<https://untobaccocontrol.org/kh/legal-challenges/initial-overview-wto-panel-decision-australia-plain-packaging/>>, accessed on 12 April 2019.

⁸⁴ *British American Tobacco UK Ltd & Ors, R (on the application of) v The Secretary of State for Health* [2016] EWCA Civ 1182 (30 November 2016) [2016] (Court of Appeal of England and Wales).

⁸⁵ *British American Tobacco v Secretary of State for Health* [2016] EWHC 1169, [2016] (Royal Courts of Justice).

⁸⁶ Decree No. 2016-1117 of 11 August 2016 on the manufacture, presentation, sale and use of tobacco products, vaping products and herbal smoking products other than tobacco (n 15).

⁸⁷ *CE, 23 décembre 2016, société JT International SA, Société d'exploitation industrielle des tabacs et des allumettes, société Philip Morris France SA et autres* [2016] (High Administrative Court).

that the State's ability to regulate for public health cannot be affected by the TRIPS, the EU Trademarks Directive, the French intellectual code and that the plain packaging measures were proportional to the health objectives and there was no violation to the right of property.⁸⁸

In 2017, Norway implemented plain packaging legislation⁸⁹ and Swedish Match, a Norwegian producer of snus- smokeless tobacco product, sought injunction against the application of plain packaging legislation to snus.⁹⁰ The Court of Appeal of Norway unanimously concluded that the measure was proportionate and necessary for protecting public health.

When tribunals judged in favour of States in all mentioned cases, they tipped the balance in favour of states and this made many critics ask whether their analysis had not been too harsh on tobacco companies and whether tribunals had not gone too far by breaching investors' rights due to public pressure.

⁸⁸ McCabe Centre for Law and Cancer, 'Challenges in domestic courts to plain (standardised) packages (WHO FCTC articles 11 and 13)' [2016] <<https://untobaccocontrol.org/kh/legal-challenges/domestic-courts/plain-packaging/>>, accessed on 18 April 2019.

⁸⁹ Standardized Packaging of Tobacco Products (n 19).

⁹⁰ *Swedish Match v Ministry of Health and Care Services (Petition for Temporary Injunction)* Case No 17-110415TVI-OBYF, 20017 (Court of Appeal).

Chapter III

Analysis

I. Meaning of investment

(a) Theory

In order to assess whether the claim of investors that states by implementing plain packaging regulations breach international law, refuse predictability and stable investment environment and deteriorate their investment, or the claim of host states that a State is sovereign, its government was chosen by the people and has a democratic power to regulate legal entities in its territory for the public good and create laws that can contradict previous commitments if done in the public interest, we first need to consider what is an investment.

Every BIT has a clause that defines what an investment means for the particular BIT. In practice, most BITs provide very broad and vague definitions. For example, Australia-India BIT provides that: ‘investment’ means: ‘every kind of asset, including intellectual property rights... (i) moveable and immovable property...(ii) shares...and any other form of participation in a company...(v) activities associated with investments, such as organisation and operation of business facilities, acquisition, exercise and disposition of property rights including intellectual property rights.’⁹¹ This definition covers virtually all investments. But for investors to prove that their property or economic actions constitute investment they need to prove that their investment also covers the requirements put by ICSID if that investor wishes to use that dispute settlement mechanism.

Article 25(1) of the ICSID Convention provides that ICSID would have jurisdiction over a case only if ‘the legal dispute ‘arises directly out of an investment’ between the host state and a national of another state.’⁹² In order to determine whether the dispute arises directly out of an investment, Tribunals have developed a standard that needs to be covered and is widely used nowadays- the *Salini* test. The test provides for four factors that need to be fulfilled in order to

⁹¹ Agreement between the Government of Australia and the Government of India on the promotion and protection of investments 1999 (The Government of Australia and the Government of the Republic of India), Article 1 ©.

⁹² ICSID Convention, Regulations and Rules (n 77).

determine if there is an investment- 1) risk, 2) contribution by the investor, 3) duration of the investment and 4) contribution to the development of the host state.⁹³

It is a tendency of Tribunals that are bound by Article 25 of ICSID Convention to give an autonomous meaning to investment governed by the *Salini* test. But in order for a claimant to succeed in its claim that there was an investment, he will have to cover the requirements of both the BIT and Article 25 of ICSID.⁹⁴

(b) Philip Morris v Uruguay

In the particular case of the Switzerland-Uruguay BIT that governs the dispute between Philip Morris and Uruguay, Article 1(2) defines investment as all classes of assets.⁹⁵

Philip Morris claimed that its ownership of subsidiary in Uruguay and the trademarks it had registered constitute an investment. The Tribunal upheld Philip Morris's claims and concluded that trademarks can be regarded as an investment in the sense of Article 25 ICSID since it covers three of the requirements of Salini test and the fourth one- contribution to the development of the host states should not be mandatory and has been dismissed by other tribunals.⁹⁶

Has the Tribunal decided that trademarks do not constitute investment this would have substantially stripped out the Tribunal of its jurisdiction and would have essentially meant that this claim should be resolved on domestic level and not international, which would have nullified the benefits of having a BIT signed.

(c) Philip Morris v Australia

The dispute between Philip Morris and Australia was governed by Australia-Hong Kong BIT.⁹⁷ Article 1(e) of the BIT provides that the term investment includes all investments, made before and after the BIT was created. The BIT also requires disputes to be resolved on UNCITRAL Rules. UNCITRAL, unlike ICSID, does not provide separate requirements on investment and

⁹³ *Salini Costruttori S.p.A. and Italstrade S.p.A. v. Kingdom of Morocco, Decision on Jurisdiction* ICSID Case No. ARB/00/4, [2001] (ICSID).

⁹⁴ Benn Mcgrady, *Implications of Ongoing Trade and Investment Disputes Concerning Tobacco: Philip Morris v. Uruguay* (2011), accessed on 17 April 2019.

⁹⁵ Agreement between the Swiss Confederation and the Oriental Republic of Uruguay on the Reciprocal Promotion and Protection of Investments (n 8).

⁹⁶ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5), para.208-209.

⁹⁷ Agreement between the Government of Hong Kong and the Government of Australia for the Promotion and Protection of Investments (n 11).

concludes that there is investment in the case where it can be proven that the investor has control and ownership over his investment.⁹⁸ The Tribunal upheld its jurisdiction.

II. Expropriation

(a) Theory

Bilateral Investment treaties nowadays have an expropriation clause, which provides for conditions under which countries may expropriate investors' property lawfully.⁹⁹ Expropriation may be direct- when governments take away foreign investment from the investor or indirect- where states act unfairly towards an investor, adopt measures that are discriminatory in nature, or violate obligations undertaken by the state towards the investor and this deprives the investor from enjoyment of his investment.¹⁰⁰

However, it has been recognised in international law that States have the right to regulate activities of all sorts within their territories- including commercial and business activities.¹⁰¹ Nevertheless, most investment treaties provide three (or four) conditions that must be met so an act of expropriation can be considered legal. Legal expropriation must be made for the public interest, non-arbitrarily, in due process and be compensated promptly, adequately and effectively.¹⁰²

However, the case law on expropriation has gone in opposite directions since some tribunals have found that in some cases states should compensate for expropriation and in others- should not.¹⁰³

In the context of plain packaging, a tobacco company can argue that packaging regulations amount to indirect expropriation since by imposing certain packaging requirements, states limit the use of trademarks and this deprives the foreign investor of enjoyment of its intellectual

⁹⁸ Tania Voon and Andrew Mitchell, 'Implications of international investment law for plain tobacco packaging: Lessons from the Hong Kong-Australia BIT' [2012], accessed on 18 April 2019.

⁹⁹ Stephen Fietta, 'Expropriation and the 'Fair and Equitable' Standard' [2006] *Journal of International Arbitration* <<http://roboalbanconuevomundo.com/pdf/bnm-memorial-de-meritos/anexo%20vii.%20doctrina/anexo%2011.pdf>>, accessed on 20 April 2019.

¹⁰⁰ Peter Isakoff, 'Defining the Scope of Indirect Expropriation for International Investments' (2013) 3(2) *The Global Business Law Review* 189 <<https://engagedscholarship.csuohio.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=https://www.google.com/&httpsredir=1&article=1033&context=gblr>>, accessed on 17 April 2019.

¹⁰¹ Inaamul Haque and Roxandra Burdescu, 'Monterrey Consensus on Financing for Development: Response Sought from International Economic Law' [2004] *Boston College International and Comparative Law Review* <<https://lawdigitalcommons.bc.edu/iclr/vol27/iss2/4/>>, accessed on 16 April 2019.

¹⁰² Dolzer and Schreuer (n 76).

¹⁰³ *Saluka Investments B.V. v. The Czech Republic*, UNCITRAL [2004] (UNCITRAL).

property.¹⁰⁴ Philip Morris has already claimed against both Australia and Uruguay that trademarks are a form of investment and such restrictions go against international investment law.

(a) Philip Morris v Australia-BIT case

Article 6(1) of the Hong Kong –Australia BIT defines expropriation as ‘deprivation of investment’. It adds four conditions for lawful expropriation : (1) due process of law, (2) public purpose, (3) non-discrimination and (4) compensation. Unfortunately, the Philip Morris – Australia case did not reach the stage of merits because the tribunal concluded that the claim is inadmissible due to abuse of rights. It was found that Philip Morris restructured its investment with the sole purpose of taking advantage of the BIT.¹⁰⁵

However, had the Tribunal allowed the case to continue to the stage of merits and given a verdict, the outcome of the case would have had important implications for future cases related to plain packaging regulations. In that respect it is important to take a closer look at the two parties’ claims and weight them.

In its request for arbitration, Philip Morris claimed that by implementing the Tobacco Plain Packaging regulation, Australia had prohibited Philip Morris to use trademarks and other distinctive symbols on tobacco boxes which had indirectly expropriated Philip Morris and its subsidiary’ s investment in Australia. Philip Morris could have also claimed that their brands had been expropriated without the payment of prompt, adequate and effective compensation and since Article 6(1) of the BIT requires for a lawful expropriation to be compensated- this would mean that Australia illegally expropriated Philip Morris’s investment, which is a clear breach of the BIT. Philip Morris could have argued that Australia’s interference substantially undermined the value of its brands.

On the other hand, Australia could have argued that it is a common position that the obligation to pay for an indirect expropriation does not arise in cases where the measure that had been adopted in a non-discriminatory manner, for the protection of the public good, in good faith

¹⁰⁴ Ben Mostafa, ‘The Sole Effects Doctrine, Police Powers and Indirect Expropriation under International Law’ (2019) 9(1) Asian Journal of International Law 98 <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/EB1C739257E355631F270A98B23F5481/S2044251318000139a.pdf/police_powers_indirect_expropriation_in_international_investment_law_and_article_313c_of_the_vclt_a_critique_of_philip_morris_v_uruguay.pdf>, accessed on 17 April 2019.

¹⁰⁵ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5), para.585.

and in achieving legitimate objectives.¹⁰⁶ Australia could have argued that Tobacco Plain Packaging Regulation was adopted in a non-discriminatory manner since the regulation covers not only foreign investors but also Australian tobacco companies and the measure does not single out particular members of the tobacco industry and provide them with more stringent conditions. Australia could have also argued that the measure was implemented in good faith since it was following its mandatory obligations as a party to the FCTC to bring itself into compliance with FCTC Article 11. Australia could have also added that the measure was taken for the public good and in achieving legitimate objectives because tobacco products are proven to cause health problems and even death to its consumers. Australia could have also claimed that Philip Morris could not have had reasonable expectations that Australia would not change its tobacco control law.

Comment

In my opinion, had the case been allowed to reach the stage of merits, Philip Morris would not have been able to prove its point on expropriation.

I would argue that the Tribunal would have reached the conclusion that the four elements required by Article 6(1) of the respective BIT are fulfilled and there is no breach of Article 6(1). On the point of non-discrimination, it would have been easy for the Australian government to prove that its measures are not directed at Philip Morris since they are unilateral. Australia could have also used its Tobacco Plain Packaging Bill Explanatory Memorandum as a proof that the government's purpose is promoting public health,¹⁰⁷ which would suffice the requirement of Article 6(1) (ii) - public purpose.

The Tribunal, I would argue, would have also concluded that the measures were taken in due process of law, since they were fair and proportionate to the objective. Tribunals have already concluded that the public purpose can be perceived as a balancing exercise between mandatory health measures and investors' right to property.¹⁰⁸ The Tribunal could have also based its decision on previous case law such as *LG& E v Argentine Republic* where it was found that it is not probable for a measure to be found 'obviously disproportionate' to the goal pursued if

¹⁰⁶ *Methanex Corporation v United States*. Final award on Jurisdiction and merits, Ad hoc- UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules (3 August 2005) Part IV, Chapter D : " As a matter of general international law, a non-discriminatory regulation for a public purpose, which is enacted in accordance with due process and, which affects, inter alios, a foreign investor or investment is not deemed expropriatory and compensable unless specific commitments had been given by the regulating government to the then putative foreign investor contemplating investment that the government would refrain from such regulation".

¹⁰⁷ Check p.1-2.

¹⁰⁸ *Voon and Mitchell* (n 102).

that goal is the public interest.¹⁰⁹ And since the FCTC Secretariat and the WHO have shown support for Australia's tobacco measures¹¹⁰ this would tilt the balance in Australia's favour.

In addition, when it comes to the FCTC argument, FCTC is an international legal instrument to which Australia is a party. As such, Australia is required by Article 7 to 'implement and adopt measures that are necessary' for keeping obligations imposed by Articles 11 and 13 of the Convention. Furthermore, Article 2 FCTC allows parties and even encourages them to 'implement measures that go beyond those required by the Convention' as long as these requirements are consistent with the provisions and international law. Moreover, if we focus on public international law, Article 30 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT)¹¹¹ provides that in cases where treaties (that are not incompatible with each other), the later treaty should prevail¹¹² and provisions of the earlier treaty apply as much as its provisions are consistent with the later treaty.¹¹³ Based on that, the Australia-Hong Kong Treaty's provisions apply only if they are not inconsistent with provisions of the FCTC.¹¹⁴ Moreover, given the fact that the FCTC becomes stronger and gets more and more recognition it would have been very probable that PMI would lose on that point.

Overall, it would have been very difficult for PMI to prove that there was expropriation since the tobacco company is not substantially deprived of its assets (which is the standard required in most investment cases). The worst-case scenario for tobacco companies would be if plain packaging causes profits to fall but since this measure applies to all tobacco companies; it would affect the market modestly.¹¹⁵

The biggest threat to Australia would have been the claim that there was a partial expropriation of trademarks. It is true that due to the Plain packaging regulation PMI could not use all of its trademarks in Australia. However, I would argue that the Tribunal could have reached the same decision as the High Court of Australia reached on that topic- namely, that the tobacco

¹⁰⁹ *LG&E Energy Corp. LG&E Capital Corp. and LG&E International, Inc .v. Argentine Republic, ICSID Case No. ARB/02/1* [2004] (ICSID).

¹¹⁰ Liberman (n 51).

¹¹¹ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969, VCLT (United Nations).

¹¹² *ibid.* Article 30(2).

¹¹³ *ibid.* Article 30(3).

¹¹⁴ Todd Weiler, 'Philip Morris vs. Uruguay: An Analysis of Tobacco Control Measures in the Context of International Investment Law' [2010] *Investor-State LawGuide* <<https://www.investorstatelawguide.com/documents/documents/IC-0130-02.pdf>>, accessed on 18 April 2019.

¹¹⁵ Andrew Mitchell and Sebastian Wurzberger, 'Boxed In? Australia's Plain Packaging Initiative and International Investment Law' (2011) 27(4) *Arbitration International* 623 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228192524_Boxed_In_Australia's_Plain_Tobacco_Packaging_Initiative_and_International_Investment_Law>, accessed on 19 April 2019.

companies still had the right to register trademarks on the territory of Australia and to maintain that registration but there was not a right to use of that trademark especially since this was done for public health reasons.¹¹⁶

In conclusion, had the Tribunal allowed the case to continue and had it reached a verdict the most probable outcome of the case-and I believe the most fair one- based on previous case law and on international law, plain packaging would have been unlikely to violate the substantive obligation against expropriation in the BIT.

(b) Philip Morris v Uruguay

Article 5(1) of the Switzerland-Uruguay BIT provides that expropriation of an investment is legal if it is done (1) for public purposes, (2) non-discriminatory, (3) in due process and (4) is compensated. PMI claimed that Uruguay deprived it substantially of its investment and thus breached Article 5(1). PMI claimed that compensation for its economic losses was due. The Tribunal reached the conclusion that there was not a substantial deprivation or positive right to use trademarks. It also concluded that the doctrine of ‘police powers’ is longstanding in international law and applies in the case of tobacco measures which means in practical terms that states have the right to regulate in the public health interest. Tribunal also reflected on the importance of the WHO FCTC and its Guidelines and concluded that public health should have an important value in international investment law.¹¹⁷

Comment

The Tribunal emphasised the importance of the FCTC for the preservation of public health and used its guidelines as a point of reference for the reasonableness of a measure. However, it could be argued that since Switzerland had not ratified the FCTC Convention, it should not be considered a subsequent agreement for the Switzerland-Uruguay BIT and its provisions should not be relied upon in respect to expropriation as required by Article 31 VCLT. However, I would argue that the Tribunal could have used customary international law, the doctrine of police powers and case law on expropriation and would have reached the same conclusion.

¹¹⁶ Liberman (n 51).

¹¹⁷ Matthew Porterfield and Christopher Byrnes, ‘Philip Morris v Uruguay: Will Investor- state arbitration send restrictions on tobacco marketing up in smoke?’ (12 July 2011) <<https://www.iisd.org/itm/2011/07/12/philip-morris-v-uruguay-will-investor-state-arbitration-send-restrictions-on-tobacco-marketing-up-in-smoke/>>, accessed on 19 April 2019.

When it comes to expropriation, the Tribunal based its award on previous case law and concluded that expropriation- even an indirect one- exists only when there is substantial deprivation of assets. I would argue that the Tribunal rightfully concluded that this was not the case here since Philip Morris International continued to be the legal and de facto owner of the subsidiary, had full control over its assets and the only result of the measure was partial loss of the profits. Which I would argue does not amount to expropriation.

I would also claim that the Tribunal's legal test on police powers doctrine is rational. It was concluded that 'protecting public health has since long been recognised as an essential manifestation of the State's police powers'.¹¹⁸ I would argue that the Tribunal followed a pattern of cases- *Techmed v Mexico*¹¹⁹, *Chemtura v Canada*,¹²⁰ *Saluka v Czech Republic*¹²¹ and *Methanex v United States*¹²² that police powers doctrine is not equal to indirect expropriation.

Although the Swiss-Uruguay BIT is an old one and unlike the new BITs is broadly worded and does not contain specific guidance to what can constitute expropriation, I believe that the Tribunal rightfully stated that the BIT needed to be read not only in its own context but in light of 'relevant rules of international law applicable between the parties'.¹²³ In practice, this means that when the Tribunal decides on the meaning of expropriation it should regard customary international law and previous decisions on police powers doctrine -which is what the Tribunal did.

In assessing the rationale of police powers doctrine, the Tribunal in *Philip Morris v Uruguay* concluded that the police powers doctrine should be deemed valid if it is done for protecting of the public health, in a non-discriminatory and proportionate manner. The Tribunal concluded that both the 80/80 Regulation and the single presentation requirement were created in that manner and I support this decision.

These measures are unilateral and non-discriminatory, imposing equal requirements on all tobacco companies in Uruguay. They are also implemented for the public good- for protecting

¹¹⁸ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5). Para.291.

¹¹⁹ *Técnicas Medioambientales Tecmed, S.A. v. The United Mexican States, Award* [2003] (ICSID).

¹²⁰ *Chemtura Corporation v. Government of Canada, UNCITRAL (formerly Crompton Corporation v. Government of Canada)* [2001] (UNCITRAL).

¹²¹ *Saluka Investments B.V. v. The Czech Republic, UNCITRAL* (n 107).

¹²² *Methanex Corporation v United States of America, Final Award on Jurisdiction and Merits, (2005) 44 ILM 1345, Inside US Trade, 19 August 2005, 12, IIC 167 (2005), 3rd August 2005, Ad Hoc Tribunal (UNCITRAL)* [2000] (UNCITRAL).

¹²³ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5).

consumers from the harmful effects of tobacco products. Although it can be argued that Uruguay did not conduct its own research on the topic of implications of tobacco products on public health due to its budget constraints I would argue that States could use evidentiary support from the FCTC and implement legislation without the need to conduct their own research. As mentioned above, Tribunals have already concluded that if a measure is taken in order to protect public health it is not probable that it will be held disproportionate to the objective.¹²⁴

Based on these observations, I would argue that the Tribunal made a valid and logical conclusion that Uruguay did not breach its international investment obligations. The outcome of the case will have important implications for the future. It will not only strengthen the position of the FCTC as an international document that has normative, legal and evidentiary power but would also encourage states to implement the FCTC. It would also give an example of a successful state defence which would encourage other states to implement tobacco control measures. And even though it is not a precedent in international investment law, it will give legal arguments for future tribunals that might have to decide on the topic of plain packaging.

III. Fair and Equitable treatment

Fair and equitable treatment appears in all investment treaties and it is the standard that is the most invoked by investors against states. However, it is also very controversial. The content of the standard is vague and since there are several different approaches to its meaning this has caused confusion in Tribunals.¹²⁵ Different Tribunals define different factors¹²⁶ that need to be taken into consideration in order to determine whether the standard has been breached but the two factors that are most commonly used are arbitrariness and legitimate expectation.

(b) Philip Morris v Australia- BIT case

Article 2(2) of the Hong Kong- Australia BIT requires investments to be accorded fair and equitable treatment at all times. Philip Morris claimed that Australia breached this substantive

¹²⁴ *LG&E Energy Corp. LG&E Capital Corp. and LG&E International, Inc .v. Argentine Republic, ICSID Case No. ARB/02/1* (n 112).

¹²⁵ Mitchell and Wurzberger (n 118).

¹²⁶ The Tribunal in *Vivendi v Argentina* concluded that fair and equitable treatment should be regarded in conformity with the principles of international law and should not be limited to the minimum standard of treatment. The Tribunal in *Chemtura v Canada* concluded that FET must be determined by reference to customary international law.

obligation by introducing the plain packaging measures. PM claimed that Australia breached their legitimate expectations and introduced the measures in arbitrary and unreasonable way. As mentioned in Chapter II, the case did not reach the merits and the Tribunal did not have to decide on the topic whether the absolute standard was breached. However, I would argue, had the case been allowed to continue, Philip Morris would not have been able to prove that Article 2(2) was breached.

Comment

In order for the Tribunal to reach the conclusion that the standard was breached it would have had to prove that the plain packaging tobacco regulation was implemented arbitrarily, which I would argue is not the case. The meaning of arbitrariness in international law is broad and mainly covers measures that ‘(1) inflict damage on the investor without serving a legitimate purpose; (2) is in disregard of due process; (3) were created based not on legal standards but on personal preference’ as determined by the tribunal in *EDF (Services) Limited v Romania*.¹²⁷

However, the Tobacco Plain Packaging Act was created for public reasons- protecting public health and wellbeing and thus has a legitimate purpose that moreover is supported on international level by the FCTC. Furthermore, the measure was created based on scientific data collected by both Australian Health Authorities and international authorities.¹²⁸ Tribunals have described breach of due process as conducts that ‘manifestly violate the requirements of consistency, transparency and non-discrimination’.¹²⁹ I would argue that TPPA does not represent any of these since consultations on its implementation were done publicly and transparently, Australia had consistently expressed its desires to implement more stringent regulations and has implemented them in a non-discriminatory manner that covers all tobacco producers equally.

The second factor that is commonly used to determine FET standard is legitimate expectations. Had the tribunal allowed the case to continue, Philip Morris would have emphasised that Australia breached its legitimate expectations that the regulatory environment will not change in the future and Philip Morris was misled to invest in Australia based on these expectations. I would argue that this claim would have also failed.

¹²⁷ *EDF (Services) Limited v. Romania, ICSID Case No. ARB/05/13* [2007] (ICSID).

¹²⁸ See Chapter II (V).

¹²⁹ *Saluka Investments B.V. v. The Czech Republic, UNCITRAL* (n 107)

It is commonly accepted by Tribunals that ‘legitimate expectations’ argument can be invoked only if the State made specific assurances to the investor prior the investment.¹³⁰ However, an investor cannot claim it was legitimately expecting something that was contrary to host state policies if these policies were known prior the investment.¹³¹ Moreover, Australia has been vocal about its intentions since 2005 when it ratified the FCTC. Apart from that, Philip Morris could not have reasonably expected that the tobacco regulations would never change especially since more and more scientific data was collected on the dangers of tobacco products. In view of this, I would conclude that Philip Morris would not have a likelihood in succeeding to prove that Article 2(2) of the Hong-Kong –Australia BIT was breached.

(a) Philip Morris v Uruguay

In its claim against Uruguay, Philip Morris claimed that Article 3(1) and (2) of the Switzerland-Uruguay BIT were breached.¹³² The tobacco company alleged that by introducing plain packaging measures Uruguay had obstructed the use, enjoyment, sale and growth of its investment and had breached the fair and equitable treatment that is owed to Philip Morris as an investor. The tribunal found that neither of the two measures breached the FET clause.

Comment

As mentioned above, the concept of fair and equitable treatment encompasses the doctrines of legitimate expectations and arbitrariness. However, it is not easy to prove that this standard was breached because it serves not as an insurance for investors that they will never be disappointed in governmental policies but as a standard, that protects investors from manifest mistakes in governmental policies or lack of transparency in creating these policies that leads to economic losses for investors.¹³³ However, there needs to be a very strong evidence in order to prove that the standard was breached. I would argue that the Tribunal rightfully concluded that that was not the case here.

¹³⁰ *Glamis Gold, Ltd. v. The United States of America, UNCITRAL, Award, Jun.8, 2009(620.766)* [2003] (UNCITRAL)

¹³¹ *International Thunderbird Gaming Corporation v. The United Mexican States, UNCITRAL* [2002] (UNCITRAL).

¹³² 3(1) ‘...shall not obstruct through unjustified or discriminatory measures the management, use, enjoyment, growth...of investments’; 3(2) Each Contracting party shall ensure within its territory a just and equitable treatment of investments and investors of the other contracting party’.

¹³³ Weiler (n 117).

On arbitrariness, the Tribunal concluded that the single presentation requirement and the 80/80 Regulation imposed by the Uruguayan Government were not arbitrary and were created in attempt to address a public concern and in good faith.¹³⁴ Here, the Tribunal adopted the approach put forward by the International Court of Justice in *Ellectronica Sicula S.p.A. (ELSI)*¹³⁵: arbitrary act is ‘a wilful disregard of due process of law, an act which shocks, or at least surprises, a sense of judicial propriety’.¹³⁶ I believe that the Tribunal rightfully concluded that Uruguay’s actions were not disregarding due process, nor were they discriminatory. In order to prove its point here, PMI had to demonstrate that the tobacco measures were created and implemented in a non-transparent environment. However, Uruguay implemented the FCTC and the Uruguayan President Vasquez made many public statements on the desire of Uruguay to keep its international obligations and work to achieve its final goal- dramatical reduction of tobacco consumption.¹³⁷

Just like in the case of Australia, Uruguay did not create discriminatory measures since both regulations put similar requirements on all tobacco producers, irrespective of their nationality.

When it comes to legitimate expectations, PMI claimed that Uruguay’s measures were inconsistent with its expectations that PMI would be free to enjoy its trademarks. However, the Tribunal held that this doctrine should not be used in the particular case since the Uruguay government made no specific representation prior to investment.¹³⁸ I do believe that the majority made a logical conclusion since Uruguay had already become a party to FCTC and as such was obliged to implement more stringent measures against tobacco products in order to fulfil its international obligations. Moreover, PMI must have been aware of this fact.¹³⁹

On the topic of trademarks, the Tribunal concluded that trademarks are not positive rights that allow the use of trademarks but negative rights that constrain use. I would argue that the Tribunal based its conclusion on Uruguayan law, but also on international and regional

¹³⁴ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5), para.409.

¹³⁵ *Ellectronica Sicula S.p.A. (ELSI) v Italy* [1989] (International Court of Justice).

¹³⁶ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5), para.390.

¹³⁷ Weiler (n 117).

¹³⁸ *Philip Morris Brands Sarl, Philip Morris Products S.A. and Abal Hermanos S.A. v Oriental Republic of Uruguay* (n 5), para.429-430.

¹³⁹ McCabe Centre for Law and Cancer, ‘The Award on the Merits in Philip Morris v Uruguay : implications for WHO FCTC implementation’ [2016] <http://www.mccabecentre.org/downloads/Knowledge_Hub/McCabe_Centre_paper_on_Uruguay_award.pdf>, accessed on 20 May 2019.

agreements and their position on trademarks and the rights they confer. TRIPS Agreements¹⁴⁰ in its Article 16 provides that the owner of the trademark has exclusive right to exclude other people from using it, but nowhere does it give absolute rights to owners to use trademarks in any circumstance. Nor does the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property,¹⁴¹ which is an international agreement on trademarks and patents. I would argue that the Tribunal rightfully concluded that the right to own a trademark is not absolute but a relative one. Trademarks can be used against other persons to protect the intellectual property but it cannot be used against the state when the state is using its sovereign power to create regulations especially if these regulations are created for the public good. In that sense, it can also be argued that trademarks cannot guarantee that the product will be sold and put on the market regardless of other legal regulations.¹⁴²

Based on these arguments, I believe that the Tribunal decision was logical, reasonable and fair-based on the evidence of the case, the provisions of the Switzerland-Uruguay BIT and the developments in international investment law.

IV. Trade Law

Tobacco plain packaging regulation also left its mark on trade law. After Ukraine challenged Australia's regulation, the WTO was bound to release a panel report on the regulation and its compatibility with international trade law.¹⁴³ The Panel dismissed Ukraine's claims and came to the conclusion that the measure was not breaching TBT Agreement since it is not more trade restrictive than necessary under Article 2.2. The Panel also concluded that the measure's trade restrictiveness had to be balanced with its public health agenda and 'it is widely recognised, and undisputed that the public health consequences of the use of, and exposure to, tobacco,

¹⁴⁰ Agreement on Trade- Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights 1995, TRIPS Agreements (World Trade Organisation), accessed on 21 May 2019.

¹⁴¹ Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property 1979 (World Intellectual Property Organisation).

¹⁴² *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* (n 12).

¹⁴³ Lewis H Haney and others, *Public health and plain packaging of cigarettes: Legal issues* (4th and enl. ed. Edward Elgar 2012), accessed on 18 May 2019.

including in Australia, are particularly grave.’¹⁴⁴ The Panel also found that there was no less trade restrictive measure that would achieve the same goal.¹⁴⁵

The Panel’s decision focused on the second argument of Ukraine that Australia’s TPPA was breaching the TRIPS Agreement by imposing regulations, which obstruct the right of ownership and use of trademarks of tobacco companies. The Panel’s legal interpretation of TRIPS led to the conclusion that ‘Article 16.1 does not establish a trademark owner’s right to use its registered trademark. Rather, Article 16.1 only provides for a registered trademark owner’s right to prevent certain activities by unauthorised parties under the conditions set out in the first sentence of Article 16.1’.¹⁴⁶ The strongest argument of Ukraine- that TPPA breached Article 20 TRIPS- stated that the TPPA Scheme constituted an unjustifiable encumbrance on the use of trademarks. The Panel dismissed Ukraine’s challenges on that point and found that TPPA’s requirements on plain packaging constituted special requirements for the purposes of Article 20 of TPPA since it ‘permits the use of word marks on tobacco retail packaging and on cigars only in prescribed form’.¹⁴⁷ The Panel also concluded that the use of trademarks could go beyond just commercial activities of buying and selling of tobacco products¹⁴⁸ and could go beyond use just for purposes of distinguishing the goods and services of one Tobacco Company from another.¹⁴⁹ Hence, the Panel concluded that TPPA constitutes special requirements imposed on tobacco companies and this encumbers ‘the use of trademark in the course of trade’ as defined by Article 20 TRIPS.¹⁵⁰ However, it also concluded that TPPA justifiably encumbers trade since the special requirements imposed are an important tool for the protection of social interest.¹⁵¹ Another argument the Panel provided was that creating standardised packages is not the only tool to achieve the appeal of cigarettes but nevertheless is a cornerstone of the initiative¹⁵² and the reason behind the implementation of the measure is sufficient to support the obstruction of trade.¹⁵³ One of the most important conclusions the Panel reached was that the FCTC and its Guidelines are important international legal documents providing guidance on public health and reaffirmed that ‘few interests are more vital and important than protecting

¹⁴⁴ *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* (n 12). para.7.1208, 7.1310.

¹⁴⁵ *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* (n 12). para.7.1324, 7.1731.

¹⁴⁶ *ibid.* para.7.1978.

¹⁴⁷ *ibid.* para.7.2241.

¹⁴⁸ *ibid.* para.7.2261.

¹⁴⁹ *Ibid.* para.7.2286.

¹⁵⁰ *Ibid.* para.7.2292.

¹⁵¹ *Ibid.* para.7.2592.

¹⁵² *Ibid.* para.7.2593.

¹⁵³ *Ibid.* para.7.2604.

human beings from health risks'.¹⁵⁴ The Panel took the stand that by implementing the TPPA, Australia 'has pursued its relevant domestic public health objectives in line with the emerging multilateral public health policies in the area of tobacco control as reflected in the FCTC and its Guidelines'.¹⁵⁵ Thus, the Panel found in favour of Australia and dismissed Ukraine's claims.

Comment

I would argue that the decision that was the third consecutive victory for Australia's tobacco plain packaging was right and the Panel's findings have a big importance for future trade law developments.

Although TRIPS is an international legal agreement created for the purpose of protecting intellectual property rights, it contains provisions protecting public health. Article 8 of the TRIPS provides that:

Members may, in formulating or amending their laws and regulations, adopt measures necessary to protect public health and nutrition, and to promote the public interest in sectors of vital importance to their socio-economic and technological development, provided that such measures are consistent with the provisions of this Agreement.

I would argue that the Panel rightfully concluded that TPPA is justified under Article 8(1) TRIPS.

In 2001, the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health¹⁵⁶ was signed. The Doha Declaration had implications on TRIPS. Paragraph 4 of the Declaration strengthened Article 8 by providing that 'TRIPS should not prevent members from taking measures to protect public health'. This gave more rights to countries to implement measures that are needed to enhance public health.¹⁵⁷ And as Article 31(3)(a) of the Vienna Convention of the Law of Treaties requires, since the Doha Declaration was signed after the TRIPS Agreement, the TRIPS Agreement must be interpreted in light of the Doha Declaration and its Paragraph 4 when it comes to measures implemented for protecting public health objectives. I agree with the Panel's legal finding that TPPA requirements obstruct consumers from distinguishing between brands and this harms tobacco companies.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid. para.7.1311

¹⁵⁵ Ibid. para.7.2604.

¹⁵⁶ THE DOHA DECLARATION ON THE TRIPS AGREEMENT AND PUBLIC HEALTH 2001 (World Health Organisation).

¹⁵⁷ Carlos Correa, 'Implications of the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health' [2002] <https://www.who.int/medicines/areas/policy/WHO_EDM_PAR_2002.3.pdf>, accessed on 15 May 2019.

However, I would argue that if we read Article 20 in light of Article 8 TRIPS and Paragraph 4 of Doha Declaration, this grants a lot of flexibility to countries to enact legislation for public health protection.¹⁵⁸ And respectively this means that TPPA does not breach TRIPS.

On the argument presented by Ukraine that TPPA breached TBT, I believe that the Panel's findings were supported by legal evidence and its decision was right.

As the Panel found- TPPA 'by reducing the use of tobacco products, it reduced the volume of imported tobacco products on the Australian market'.¹⁵⁹ However, measures under Article 2.2 TBT can be trade-restrictive only if there is another available measure that is less-trade restrictive, which would achieve the same health objective of the country implementing this legislation.¹⁶⁰ The complainants in the case proposed the increase in taxation of tobacco products in Australia as an alternative measure.¹⁶¹ However, I would argue that the Panel reached the right conclusion that taxes would also be trade-restrictive¹⁶² but would not achieve the same objective. FCTC provides that images and messages conveyed by tobacco products should be controlled in order to reduce the appeal of tobacco products and raising taxes would not contribute to this health objective although it would have financial consequences for the consumer. In that respect, I believe that the Panel reached the right conclusion that the risk for public health of not-implementing TPPA would be too grave which means that TPPA does not breach TBT.

Although it could be difficult to conclude what will be the implications of Australia's win in WTO, especially due to the fact that the future of WTO is not clear due to the ongoing US's blockage of appointments to the Appellate body, the decision is an important vindication of Australia's tobacco control legislation. However, if WTO survives its crisis, the decision will offer legal background and justification for future panels to decide that countries have flexibility in implementing legislation on public health matters.¹⁶³

¹⁵⁸ Andrew Mitchell, 'Australia's Move to the Plain Packaging of cigarettes and its WTO compatibility' (2010) 5(2) Asian journal of WTO and international health law and policy <<http://tobacco.cleartheair.org.hk/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/SSRN-id1729483.pdf>>, accessed on 15 May 2019.

¹⁵⁹ *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* (n 12). Para.7.1208.

¹⁶⁰ Voon (n 61).

¹⁶¹ *Australia — Certain Measures Concerning Trademarks, Geographical Indications and Other Plain Packaging Requirements Applicable to Tobacco Products and Packaging* (n 12), para.7.1474.

¹⁶² *Ibid.* para.7.1491.

¹⁶³ Gary Fooks and Anna Gilmore, 'International Trade law, plain packaging and tobacco industry political activity: The Trans-Pacific Partnership' (2014) 23(1) Tobacco Control 1 <<https://tobaccocontrol.bmj.com/content/tobaccocontrol/23/1/e1.full.pdf>>, accessed on 17 May 2019.

The recent tobacco outcomes led to the historic Article 29(5) of the Trans-Pacific Partnership Agreement (TPP)¹⁶⁴ that allows countries to block investors from using the investor-state dispute settlement mechanism in cases where investors argue against tobacco control measures.¹⁶⁵ Even though the TPP is not in force since the USA withdrew its signature this tobacco-carve out shows the recent tendency of public interest talking precedents over private rights.¹⁶⁶

V. High Court case

The High Court case is different from the previous cases since it is a domestic case and the decision of the court is based on domestic jurisdiction and specific provision of the Australian Constitution and not international legislation. The decision that the High Court reached was based on the rule in the Constitution of Australia that the Commonwealth did not benefit in any way from its implementation of the TPPA and there was no acquisition of property, which meant that the TPPA should not be invalidated. However, the High Court did not have to provide a decision on the merits of tobacco plain packaging itself.

This in practice means that if tobacco plain packaging were to be implemented in another domestic jurisdiction, different set of rights and duties were to be invoked.¹⁶⁷ However, while each case would be argued and resolved in its separate context, cases do not exist in isolation. In that sense, the High Court decision is important since it adds to the pile of decisions which upheld tobacco plain packaging and strengthens States' efforts to reduce tobacco consumption

VI. Implications of Tobacco plain packaging on Trade and Investment Law

¹⁶⁴ The Trans- Pacific Partnership, TPP (Office of the United States Trade Representative).

¹⁶⁵ Article 29(5): A Party may elect to deny the benefits of investor-state dispute settlement mechanism with respect to claims challenging a tobacco control measure of the Party. Such a claim shall not be submitted to arbitration if a Party has made such a selection. For greater certainty, if a party elects to deny benefits with respect to such claims, any such claim shall be dismissed.

¹⁶⁶ Sergio Puig and Gregory Shaffer, 'A Breakthrough with the TPP: The Tobacco Carve-Out' (2016) 16(2) Yale Journal of Health Policy, Law and Ethics 327 <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2772277>, accessed on 29 May 2019.

¹⁶⁷ Liberman (n 51).

Notwithstanding the different scenarios that different BITs and IIAs may create in the future, the cases of Philip Morris v Uruguay and the three cases of Philip Morris against Australia have already played an important role in international investment law.¹⁶⁸ The resolution of the disputes provided some clarification on the doctrine of ‘police powers’ under international investment law and the ability of states to use it against investors in tobacco control cases. These cases also provided interpretation of the doctrine of reasonable expectations of tobacco investors, which is likely to dissuade other tobacco companies from irresponsibly initiating a case based on that claim in the future. Even though in international investment law precedent does not exist, the resolutions of the disputes on the topic of public health grounds is important and the fact that all tribunals in question reached the conclusion that the WHO FCTC and its Guidelines have legal and evidentiary weight and can be used to back states’ tobacco plain packaging measures. This gives some legal certainty that the FCTC can be used in the future by Tribunals and it will receive more and more recognition as a legally binding instrument. All tribunals reached the ground-breaking conclusion that plain packaging is not an unjustifiable encumbrance to intellectual property rights of tobacco producers because plain packaging is an important part of achieving the public health interest and the reasons behind plain packaging regulations are enough to support the implementation of these measures, which will have important implications for the future since it will give more power and confidence to states to implement their own tobacco plain packaging regulations and follow the example of Australia and Uruguay. This big step has helped and would help more countries (especially smaller and poorer ones) to overcome the chill effect and implement public policies without fear of litigation, and financial losses. Tribunals also added to the case law on compensation and indirect expropriation and tilted the balance in favour of non-compensable regulatory measures that might lead to more clarification on that matter and become a precedent for future Tribunals.

Last but not least, the Tribunals have come to the conclusion that they should not be second-guessing the regulatory decisions of states on public health grounds if these decisions are taken in good faith and are not discriminatory. This can be perceived as the biggest win for countries and a step closer to finding the final solution of the dispute on which is more important- the right to health or the right to wealth.

¹⁶⁸ Luke Nottage, ‘Consumer Product Safety Regulation and Investor-State Arbitration Policy and Practice after Philip Morris Asia v Australia: Legal Studies Research Paper No. 12/26’ (2011) 22(1 and 2) Australian Product Liability Reporter 154 <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2041680>, accessed on 21 May 2019.

When we analyse the cases, we need to note the devastating effect that FCTC had on the claims of Philip Morris. Moreover, given the fact that BITs require tribunals to prove that States implemented legislation in a grave breach of bad faith in order to judge in favour of tobacco companies (which is extremely difficult to prove) – it is understandable that Philip Morris had a very little chance of winning any of its cases. Which means that if the situation stays the same and nothing changes it will be highly doubtful that in the future a tobacco company would be able to surmount the threshold that these tribunals have set. Which also means that the pendulum has swung in the opposite direction and now the power lies in States. But there is no balance between the rights of States and the rights of investors yet again.

Chapter IV

Solutions

Australia and Uruguay have won their legal battles and several years later their plain packaging legislations came into force. However, New Zealand's plain packaging legislation- an almost identical bill to the Australian one, took almost 7 years to come into force.¹⁶⁹ It is unclear why it took so many years for New Zealand to implement its legislation but several factors can be taken into mind: New Zealand's fear that there is a risk for its trade and investment agreements, industry lobbyist and bias against intervention. Nevertheless, New Zealand had the same legitimate grounds as Australia for introducing plain packaging and it is possible that the so called phenomenon of regulatory chill caused the government's reluctance. Three of the biggest concerns that governments experience during regulatory chill is fear of the financial burden they might experience in a case of loss, loss of investors due to bad reputation and fears based on previous litigation.¹⁷⁰

However, when governments discard a policy that is good for the public health in fear of financial penalties the actual cost that is paid is the cost of failure of health regulations and this cost is borne by citizens since their right to health is diminished.¹⁷¹ In order to avoid paying this cost a solution to the problem should be found and a balance between the rights of investors and states should be determined so there are no more ambiguities.

I. Governmental solutions

One solution for finding a balance between the rights of states and the rights of investors that has been proposed is for governments who fear that litigation may be used against them to renegotiate their bilateral trade agreements and their international investment agreements with other countries to exclude tobacco control measures or when signing new BITs and IIAs to put tobacco control measures as an exception to the rule. This will not allow tobacco producers to

¹⁶⁹ The New Zealand Government opened a public consultation on plain packaging in 2012 and the Tobacco Standardised regime came into force on March 2018.

¹⁷⁰ Kelsey (n 3).

¹⁷¹ Jennifer L Tobin, 'The Social Cost of International Investment Agreements: The Case of Cigarette Packaging' (2018) 32(02) *Ethics int aff* 153 <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/ethics-and-international-affairs/article/social-cost-of-international-investment-agreements-the-case-of-cigarette-packaging/E90D06895D35F7412F06FA80EF38FED9>>, accessed on 28 May 2019.

start legal objections against the country and it will minimise the chance of monetary compensation and pressure against the government to change the law.¹⁷² Thus states would not have to subject their tobacco control measures to any WTO or investment tribunals. Australia is one of the countries that has already declared its intentions to no longer have Investor-State dispute resolution provisions in its future BITs and IIAs.¹⁷³

II. FCTC takes precedence over trade and investment law

If a solution is to be found on a larger scale, a possible option is an international consensus negotiated by all member states of WTO and Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) that FCTC takes precedence over international trade and investment law. Thus, it would be clear for courts that health objectives should not be subordinate to economic rights of investors and a clearer and consistent outcome of legal cases would be possible.¹⁷⁴

III. Changing international trade law

A change of WTO law can be very beneficial to finding a balance between stakeholders. Countries have a big incentive to comply with WTO law because otherwise they will have to pay a big fine or change laws and currently the only possible defence for countries implementing plain packaging requirements is Article XX(b) of the GATT that provides an exception to WTO rules on public health. However, the scope of Article XX(b) is very narrow since it allows exceptions only if they are ‘necessary’ to protect human life.¹⁷⁵ WTO law also requires that the ‘necessary’ standard is met only if the measure at hand is the ‘least trade restrictive’ measure. And in the case of plain packaging it can be argued that there are less restrictive measures that can achieve the same goals- such as imposing taxes on tobacco products.¹⁷⁶

¹⁷² Rapchael Lencucha and Jeffrey Drope, ‘Plain packaging: an opportunity for improved international policy coherence?’ (2015) 30(2) Health Promotion International 281 <<https://academic.oup.com/heapro/article/30/2/281/562360>>, accessed on 24 May 2019.

¹⁷³ J. Kurtz, ‘Australia’s Rejection of Investor-State Arbitration: Causation, Omission and Implication’ (2012) 27(1) ICSID Review 65, accessed on 24 May 2019.

¹⁷⁴ Cynthia Callard, ‘Why trade and investment liberalisation may threaten effective tobacco control efforts’ (2001) 10(1) Tobacco Control 68 <<https://tobaccocontrol.bmj.com/content/tobaccocontrol/10/1/68.full.pdf>>

¹⁷⁵ GATT- General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade 1947 (World Trade Organisation), accessed on 25 May 2019.

¹⁷⁶ Callard (n 153).

IV. Developing a uniform standard for indirect expropriation

As seen in Chapter III, the definition of indirect expropriation is not clear and this has led to many case decisions that had completely opposite outcomes. This, however, is one of the main causes for such ambiguity in the international investment law and in particular in the case of plain packaging regulations.¹⁷⁷ And this gives big incentives and hopes to tobacco companies to initiate a legal case in the hope that in their particular case the outcome may be positive. However, if investment tribunals identify specific criteria which a conduct must cover in order to amount to indirect expropriation then the number of potential cases would potentially decrease and states would also be more confident in implementing tobacco control legislation.

V. Future of plain packaging measures

One of the biggest consequences of implementing these solutions would be that finally there would be clarity on the topic of implications that tobacco plain packaging has on international trade and investment law. This would send a clear message to countries around the world and governments that have previously backed out of this type of measures would reconsider their position and adopt more restricting measures on tobacco control.¹⁷⁸

International Investment Law needs to change in order to accommodate both the States and the investors. But the solutions to this problem need to be very thoroughly evaluated before being used. We need to keep in mind that not all proposed solutions will have the desired effect and some may even create a bigger imbalance. If States opt for the carve out scenario this will take away even more of the powers of investors to defend themselves and their investments which will have a negative effect on international investment law since investors will no longer believe that it can protect their interests. However, a mix of the other solutions might be a step in the right direction

¹⁷⁷ Isakoff (n 104).

¹⁷⁸ Ankita Ritwik, 'Tobacco Packaging Arbitration and the State's Ability to Legislate' (2013) 54(2) Harvard International Law Journal 523
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283232890_Tobacco_Packaging_Arbitration_and_the_State's_Ability_to_Legislate>, accessed on 23 May 2019.

Conclusion

IAs and BITs have long been accused of moving decision-making processes from national to international level and providing international corporations with yet another supranational forum where they can challenge states' sovereignty and their ability to introduce new legislation. And recently, these claims have been based on public health-related provisions and their alleged inconsistency with treaty commitments.

Philip Morris's cases against Australia and Uruguay and the other cases that followed suit have led to allegations that investor-state arbitration is obstructing governments from regulating and protecting the wellbeing of their citizens. On the other hand, defenders of IAs claim that Bilateral Trade Agreements are just like any other international agreement and states need to give up some of their sovereignty in order to benefit from foreign investments that come with BITs. But what if this loss of government sovereignty leads to substantial social costs because the interests of the citizens are not part of the equation?

Investment disputes' main role is not to earn monetary compensation for tobacco companies but to try to prevent countries from implementing aggressive tobacco control regulations such as standardised packaging and graphic warnings or to try to delay their implementation. Philip Morris did not target Australia because of its strong tobacco industry or growing market for tobacco products. Instead, Philip Morris targeted it because Australia is a leader in tobacco control and tobacco producers are concerned that other countries, with bigger tobacco markets will follow suit. Nor did it target Uruguay for commercial reasons. Uruguay has a population of only 3.5 million people and with a market share that small, political incentives were much bigger than economic ones. Tobacco companies' attempts to secure their investments do not end with legal cases. In the recent years Philip Morris International expressed support for the so called TRIPS-Plus agreement that is supposed to impose stricter rules on protection of trademarks and thus give more rights to tobacco companies in their fight against States.

The topic of plain packaging and its compatibility with international investment law and the WTO regime is important. A balance of interests needs to be found because concerns that tobacco plain packaging breaches trade and investment obligations, supported by tobacco companies' objections and legal cases, may have a chilling effect on governments that want to implement plain packaging. On the other hand, the growing tension between advocates for

tobacco control and investor- state arbitration may have negative consequences for the future of investor-state arbitration.

Important breakthrough has been achieved by the outcome of the two cases of Philip Morris against Australia and Uruguay. The messages that can be found in the Tribunals' decisions are clear: the intellectual property rights of the Tobacco companies are 'negative rights' that exclude others from using trademarks, rather than positive rights to use; Tobacco Plain Packaging Regulations around the world are no different from other schemes requiring health and safety warnings and should not be treated differently; Plain Packaging Schemes do not fully constrain tobacco companies since they allow continued use of brand names and this does not completely deprive tobacco companies of their profit-making abilities. The Tribunals against Australia and Uruguay also explained that in a changing world, investors should not expect that the laws will never change, especially tobacco regulations, since more and more research is conducted on how dangerous to health tobacco products can be. This should not come as a surprise to tobacco producers since they should be aware themselves of the dangers their own products possess. And dealing with dangerous products should entail a higher threshold than other types of products when it comes to legitimate expectations- and mere reduction of sales cannot meet that threshold. Furthermore, Tribunals concluded that even though Tobacco companies may have lost some of their commercial value, commercial value is not absolute- since intellectual property rights are created first and foremost to serve public purposes. Hence, they do not operate above or separately from other laws created to serve public purposes. And while each tobacco challenge is decided in the context of different investment treaty and precedents are not binding on tribunals, no challenge to plain packaging regulations can exist in isolation, especially since the ratification of the FCTC that binds countries globally.

Nevertheless, there has been concerns about FCTC implementation and its relationship with international investment agreements but the decisions in the cases of Philip Morris against Australia and Uruguay strengthened the basis for tobacco plain packaging regulations and gave states legal, evidentiary and normative power to create and implement plain packaging regulations to protect their citizens' health.

However, FCTC implementation cannot be viewed as a final victory for States and defenders of tobacco control. Some provisions of FCTC continue to be challenged in courts by tobacco companies in WTO, international investment tribunals and even on domestic level. FCTC will

become a complete victory only after the uncertainties as to its implementation and validity are clarified by courts and legislators. In that respect, each case is an opportunity for Tribunals to enhance the position of FCTC. The decisions in favour of Australia and Uruguay's plain packaging legislations have already boosted the confidence among the other state parties to FCTC to implement plain packaging regulations in their own jurisdictions and have reinforced the legality of pursuing health objectives at the expense of economic rights of tobacco companies.

We need to consider that other products such as pharmaceuticals and prescription-only drugs are heavily regulated in nearly all countries, but cigarettes which are proven to cause the death of 50% of their long-term users are not. In most countries cigarettes are sold freely, with no restrictions on packages and with weak policies on smoking prevention which creates a paradox: lifesaving drugs are heavily regulated and life-harming drugs are not regulated enough. And plain tobacco packaging might be the key to solve this paradox. Because a balance between the right to wealth and the right to health needs to finally be reached.

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APPENDIX 1

Australian Plain Packaging Requirements models

Figure 1: Australian requirements for the cigarette pack- front

Source: Tobacco Plain Packaging- Your Guide, Australian Government, Department of Health, 2014. Available at: <http://www.health.gov.au/internet/main/publishing.nsf/Content/tppbook#top>.

Figure 2: Australian requirements for the cigarette pack – rear

Source: Tobacco Plain Packaging- Your Guide, Australian Government, Department of Health, 2014. Available at: <http://www.health.gov.au/internet/main/publishing.nsf/Content/tppbook#top>.

Figure 3: Cigar tube- front

Figure 4: Cigar tube- back

Source: Tobacco Plain Packaging- Your Guide, Australian Government, Department of Health, 2014. Available at: <http://www.health.gov.au/internet/main/publishing.nsf/Content/tpbook#top>.

APPENDIX 2

Plain Packaging around the World

Figure 5: Uruguay- Plain Packages

Source: Uruguay adopts tobacco plain packaging, NCD Alliance, Available at <https://ncdalliance.org/news-events/news/uruguay-adopts-tobacco-plain-packaging>.

Figure 6: Philip Morris Cigarettes in Uruguay

Source: Suisse-Uruguay. Philip Morris, le géant du tabac sis à Lausanne, contre le gouvernement uruguayen, A l'encontre. Available at: <http://alencontre.org/ameriques/amelat/uruguay/suisse-uruguay-philip-morris-le-geant-du-tabac-sis-a-lausanne-contre-le-gouvernement-uruguayen.html>.

Figure 7 : Health Warning Evolution in Uruguay

Source: L'Uruguay e la Philip Morris, Domande. Available at: <https://redazioneunacitta.wordpress.com/2014/05/16/luruguay-e-la-philip-morris/>.

Figure 8: Health Warning Evolution in Australia

Source: Plain packaging: A logical progression for tobacco control in one of the world's 'darkest markets', Bayly, M. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273946512_Plain_packaging_A_logical_progression_for_tobacco_control_in_one_of_the_world's_'darkest_markets'.

Figure 9: UK's Standardised Plain Packaging

Source: ASH, Standardised Plain Packaging. Available at: <http://ash.org.uk/category/information-and-resources/packaging-labelling-information-and-resources/standardised-plain-packaging/>.

Figure 10: EU's plain packaging models

Source: EU Commission Memo: Questions & Answers: New rules for tobacco products. Available at: http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-14-134_en.htm.

APPENDIX 3

WTO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control- Articles and Guidelines

Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control - Packaging and labelling of tobacco products

1. Each Party shall, within a period of three years after entry into force of this Convention for that Party, adopt and implement, in accordance with its national law, effective measures to ensure that:
 - a. tobacco product packaging and labelling do not promote a tobacco product by any means that are false, misleading, deceptive or likely to create an erroneous impression about its characteristics, health effects, hazards or emissions, including any term, descriptor, trademark, figurative or any other sign that directly or indirectly creates the false impression that a particular tobacco product is less harmful than other tobacco products. These may include terms such as “low tar”, “light”, “ultra-light”, or “mild”; and
 - b. each unit packet and package of tobacco products and any outside packaging and labelling of such products also carry health warnings describing the harmful effects of tobacco use, and may include other appropriate messages. These warnings and messages:
 - shall be approved by the competent national authority,
 - shall be rotating,
 - shall be large, clear, visible and legible,
 - should be 50% or more of the principal display areas but shall be no less than 30% of the principal display areas,
 - may be in the form of or include pictures or pictograms.
2. Each unit packet and package of tobacco products and any outside packaging and labelling of such products shall, in addition to the warnings specified in paragraph 1(b) of this Article, contain information on relevant constituents and emissions of tobacco products as defined by national authorities.
3. Each Party shall require that the warnings and other textual information specified in paragraphs 1(b) and paragraph 2 of this Article will appear on each unit packet and package of tobacco products and any outside packaging and labelling of such products in its principal language or languages.
4. For the purposes of this Article, the term “outside packaging and labelling” in relation to tobacco products applies to any packaging and labelling used in the retail sale of the product.

Sources: Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control - Packaging and labelling of tobacco products. Available at: https://www.who.int/tobacco/industry/product_regulation/art_11_fctc/en.

Paragraph 3 of the Guidelines for implementation of Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

Globally, many people are not fully aware of, misunderstand or underestimate the risks for morbidity and premature mortality due to tobacco use and exposure to tobacco smoke. Well-designed health warnings and messages on tobacco product packages have been shown to be a cost-effective means to increase public awareness of the health effects of tobacco use and to be effective in reducing tobacco consumption. Effective health warnings and messages and other tobacco product packaging and labelling measures are key components of a comprehensive, integrated approach to tobacco control.

Paragraph 12 of the Guidelines for implementation of Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

Article 11.1(b) (iv) of the Convention specifies that health warnings and messages on tobacco product packaging and labelling should be 50% or more, but no less than 30%, of the principal display areas. Given the evidence that the effectiveness of health warnings and messages increases with their size, Parties should consider using health warnings and messages that cover more than 50% of the principal display areas and aim to cover as much of the principal display areas as possible. The text of health warnings and messages should be in bold print in an easily legible font size and in a specified style and colour(s) that enhance overall visibility and legibility.

Paragraph 46 of the Guidelines for implementation of Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

Parties should consider adopting measures to restrict or prohibit the use of logos, colours, brand images or promotional information on packaging other than brand names and product names displayed in a standard colour and font style (plain packaging). This may increase the noticeability and effectiveness of health warnings and messages, prevent the package from detracting attention from them, and address industry package design techniques that may suggest that some products are less harmful than others.

Source: Guidelines for implementation of Article 11 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (Packaging and labelling of tobacco products). Available at: https://www.who.int/fctc/guidelines/article_11.pdf.

Article 13 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control – Tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship

1. Parties recognize that a comprehensive ban on advertising, promotion and sponsorship would reduce the consumption of tobacco products.

2. Each Party shall, in accordance with its constitution or constitutional principles, undertake a comprehensive ban of all tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship. This shall include, subject to the legal environment and technical means available to that Party, a comprehensive ban on cross-border advertising, promotion and sponsorship originating from its territory. In this respect, within the period of five years after entry into force of this Convention for that Party, each Party shall undertake appropriate legislative, executive, administrative and/or other measures and report accordingly in conformity with Article 21.

3. A Party that is not in a position to undertake a comprehensive ban due to its constitution or constitutional principles shall apply restrictions on all tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship. This shall include, subject to the legal environment and technical means available to that Party, restrictions or a comprehensive ban on advertising, promotion and sponsorship originating from its territory with cross-border effects. In this respect, each Party shall undertake appropriate legislative, executive, administrative and/or other measures and report accordingly in conformity with Article 21.

4. As a minimum, and in accordance with its constitution or constitutional principles, each Party shall:

(a) prohibit all forms of tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship that promote a tobacco product by any means that are false, misleading or deceptive or likely to create an erroneous impression about its characteristics, health effects, hazards or emissions;

(b) require that health or other appropriate warnings or messages accompany all tobacco advertising and, as appropriate, promotion and sponsorship;

(c) restrict the use of direct or indirect incentives that encourage the purchase of tobacco products by the public;

(d) require, if it does not have a comprehensive ban, the disclosure to relevant governmental authorities of expenditures by the tobacco industry on advertising, promotion and sponsorship not yet prohibited. Those authorities may decide to make those figures available, subject to national law, to the public and to the Conference of the Parties, pursuant to Article 21;

- (e) undertake a comprehensive ban or, in the case of a Party that is not in a position to undertake a comprehensive ban due to its constitution or constitutional principles, restrict tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship on radio, television, print media and, as appropriate, other media, such as the internet, within a period of five years; and
- (f) prohibit, or in the case of a Party that is not in a position to prohibit due to its constitution or constitutional principles restrict, tobacco sponsorship of international events, activities and/or participants therein.

5. Parties are encouraged to implement measures beyond the obligations set out in paragraph 4.

6. Parties shall cooperate in the development of technologies and other means necessary to facilitate the elimination of cross-border advertising.

7. Parties, which have a ban on certain forms of tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship, have the sovereign right to ban those forms of cross-border tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship entering their territory and to impose equal penalties as those applicable to domestic advertising, promotion and sponsorship originating from their territory in accordance with their national law. This paragraph does not endorse or approve of any particular penalty.

8. Parties shall consider the elaboration of a protocol setting out appropriate measures that require international collaboration for a comprehensive ban on cross-border advertising, promotion and sponsorship.

Paragraph 15 of the Guidelines for implementation of Article 13 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

Packaging is an important element of advertising and promotion. Tobacco pack or product features are used in various ways to attract consumers, to promote products and to cultivate and promote brand identity, for example by using logos, colours, fonts, pictures, shapes and materials on or in packs or on individual cigarettes or other tobacco products.

Paragraph 16 of the Guidelines for implementation of Article 13 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

The effect of advertising or promotion on packaging can be eliminated by requiring plain packaging: black and white or two other contrasting colours, as prescribed by national authorities; nothing other than a brand name, a product name and/or manufacturer's name, contact details and the quantity of product in the packaging, without any logos or other features apart from health warnings, tax stamps and other government-mandated information or markings; prescribed font style and size; and standardized shape, size and materials. There should be no advertising or promotion inside or attached to the package or on individual cigarettes or other tobacco products.

Paragraph 17 of the Guidelines for implementation of Article 13 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

If plain packaging is not yet mandated, the restriction should cover as many as possible of the design features that make tobacco products more attractive to consumers such as animal or other figures, "fun" phrases, coloured cigarette papers, attractive smells, novelty or seasonal packs.

APPENDIX 4

Legislation around the World

Australia- Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011

Section 3

(1) The objects of this Act are:

(a) to improve public health by:

- (i) discouraging people from taking up smoking, or using tobacco products; and
- (ii) encouraging people to give up smoking, and to stop using tobacco products; and
- (iii) discouraging people who have given up smoking, or who have stopped using tobacco products, from relapsing; and
- (iv) reducing people's exposure to smoke from tobacco products; and

(b) to give effect to certain obligations that Australia has as a party to the Convention on Tobacco Control.

(2) It is the intention of the Parliament to contribute to achieving the objectives in subsection

(1) by regulating the retail packaging and appearance of tobacco products in order to:

- (a) reduce the appeal of tobacco products to consumers; and
- (b) increase the effectiveness of health warnings on the retail packaging of tobacco products; and
- (c) reduce the ability of the retail packaging of tobacco products to mislead consumers about the harmful effects of smoking or using tobacco products.

Source: Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011, No. 148, 2011- An Act to discourage the use of tobacco products, and for related purposes. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2011A00148>

DIRECTIVE 2014/40/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 3 April 2014¹⁷⁹

(7) Legislative action at Union level is also necessary in order to implement the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control ('FCTC') of May 2003, the provisions of which are binding on the Union and its Member States. The FCTC provisions on the regulation of the contents of tobacco products, the regulation of tobacco product disclosures, the packaging and labelling of tobacco products, advertising and illicit trade in tobacco products are particularly relevant. The Parties to the FCTC, including the Union and its Member States, adopted a set of guidelines for the implementation of FCTC provisions by consensus during various Conferences.

(27) Tobacco products or their packaging could mislead consumers, in particular young people, where they suggest that these products are less harmful. This is, for example, the case if certain words or features are used, such as the words 'low-tar', 'light', 'ultra-light', 'mild', 'natural', 'organic', 'without additives', 'without flavours' or 'slim', or certain names, pictures, and figurative or other signs. Other misleading elements might include, but are not limited to, inserts or other additional material such as adhesive labels, stickers, onserts, scratch-offs and sleeves or relate to the shape of the tobacco product itself. Certain packaging and tobacco products could also mislead consumers by suggesting benefits in terms of weight loss, sex appeal, social status, social life or qualities such as femininity, masculinity or elegance. Likewise, the size and appearance of individual cigarettes could mislead consumers by creating the impression that they are less harmful. Neither the unit packets of tobacco products nor their outside packaging should include printed vouchers, discount offers, reference to free distribution, two-for-one or other similar offers that could suggest economic advantages to consumers thereby inciting them to buy those tobacco products.

(42) The labelling and packaging of these products should display sufficient and appropriate information on their safe use, in order to protect human health and safety, should carry appropriate health warnings and should not include any misleading elements or features

¹⁷⁹ DIRECTIVE 2014/40/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 3 April 2014 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States concerning the manufacture, presentation and sale of tobacco and related products and repealing Directive 2001/37/EC 2014.

Article 10

Combined health warnings for tobacco products for smoking

1. Each unit packet and any outside packaging of tobacco products for smoking shall carry combined health warnings.

The combined health warnings shall:

c) cover 65 % of both the external front and back surface of the unit packet and any outside packaging. Cylindrical packets shall display two combined health warnings, equidistant from each other, each covering 65 % of their respective half of the curved surface;

(d) show the same text warning and corresponding colour photograph on both sides of the unit packets and any outside packaging;

Source: DIRECTIVE 2014/40/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 3 April 2014 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States concerning the manufacture, presentation and sale of tobacco and related products and repealing Directive 2001/37/EC. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/tobacco/docs/dir_201440_en.pdf.

Uruguay- Law No. 19.723

Chapter 1

Provisions Common to Neutral or Generic Packaging and Labelling of All Tobacco Products

1) Colour of all tobacco product packages.

The colour of all tobacco product packaging will be of a single one, uniform, and corresponding to Pantone 448C with matt finish (equivalent to RGB 74 65 42). The Ministry shall provide colour schemes for periods of no less than two years. This requirement is not applicable to the health pictograms and warnings regulated by Article 9 of Law No. 18,356.

2) Brands and other distinctive signs.

The brands of all tobacco products will be incorporated in a single, uniform letter style, size, position, and colour, defined by this regulation. The font shall be Lucida Sans, the colour black, with size no greater than 14, without shadows or other overlaid elements, and with a matt finish.

3) Commercial brand.

Each commercial brand on the neutral or generic packaging must conform to a single presentation for tobacco products.

Prohibitions include the use of terms, descriptive elements, figurative signs, logos or distinctive signs of any other type, such as combinations of numbers or letters that have a direct or indirect effect in creating the false impression that a certain product is less harmful than others.

4) Different forms of advertising.

The packaging of all tobacco products may not contain any type of decorative element, devices that allow it to make a sound, produce an aroma different from tobacco, include a function or feature intended to be changed after retail sale, or include adhesives or additional material inside the packet.

5) Labelling.

The bar code, name, address, and other contact information for the manufacturer, as well as all other information required by the regulation, will be located on one of the side faces of the package. The bar code will be rectangular and in black and white. The data referring to the name and address of the manufacturer will be shown in Lucida Sans font, in black, and with a size no greater than 10. On the other side face, information directed at the consumer will be included, to be defined by the Ministry of Public Health.

Source: Order No.696. Available at:

<https://www.tobaccocontrolaws.org/files/live/Uruguay/Uruguay%20-%20Ord.%20No.%20696.pdf> ,
also: <https://www.tobaccocontrolaws.org/files/live/Uruguay/Uruguay%20-%20Law%20No.%2019.723%20-%20national.pdf>.

APPENDIX 5

International Developments

LAW ADOPTED AND IN FORCE ¹⁸⁰

Australia – Tobacco Plain Packaging Act 2011

United Kingdom – Standardised Packaging of Tobacco Products Regulations 2016

France - Decree No. 2016-1117 of 11 August 2016 on the manufacture, presentation, sale and use of tobacco products, vaping products and herbal smoking products other than tobacco

Uruguay- Law No. 19.723

Turkey- Law No 7151 came into force on 1 March 2019

LAW ADOPTED BUT NOT YET IMPLEMENTED

Hungary – Decree No 239/2016

Ireland – Public Health (Standardised Packaging of Tobacco) Act 2015

Norway -Standardized Packaging of Tobacco Products 2017

New Zealand – Smoke-free Environments (Tobacco Standardised Packaging) Amendment Act 2016

Slovenia - Rules on the Plain Packaging of Tobacco Products 2020

Romania – Law on the establishment of conditions concerning the manufacture, presentation and marketing of tobacco and related products and amendments to Law No. 349/2002 on preventing the consumption of tobacco products and combating its effects 2016

Canada – Plain packaging Bill to come into force in November 2019

Singapore- Tobacco (Control of Advertisements and sale) Bill 2019

Thailand – has adopted plain packaging for tobacco products, Bill to enter into force in December 2019.

¹⁸⁰ Campaign for tobacco free kids, ‘Plain or Standardised Tobacco Packaging: International Developments- Updated February 2017’ <https://atca-africa.org/images/pdf/standardized_packaging_developments_en.pdf>

LEGISLATION BEING CONSIDERED BY PARLIAMENT

Brazil- Different packages bills introduced to the Senate in 2016

Chile – A bill to give effect to plain packaging has been proposed in 2015

Ecuador – A bill was assigned to the National Assembly in 2016

Panama- A bill was introduced to the National Assembly in 2015 but no further action has taken place so far

UNDER FORMAL GOVERNMENT CONSIDERATION

Finland- The Government National Action Plan was introduced in July 2016 but it did not include plain packaging

Sweden – It is still in talks whether legislation should include plain packaging.

POLITICAL COMMITMENTS GIVEN

Belgium- Federal Government announces it is ready to introduce plain packaging as soon as possible

South Africa – In May 2018 the Minister of Health introduced the draft Control of Tobacco Products and Electronic Delivery Systems Bill and stated the readiness of the government to introduce plain packaging

Kenya- In 2016 the Cabinet Secretary for Health that a plan for the implementation of plain packaging will be developed

United Arab Emirates- In 2014 the Ministry of Health announced its desire to introduce plain packaging legislation

Malaysia- In 2019 the Minister of Health showed his intention to follow Australia and introduce plain packaging

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